

An updated geographic analysis of regional variation in *Anthocharis midea* (Hübner, [1809]) and review of dos Passos & Klots (1969) and Gatrell (1998).

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ABSTRACT: Subspecies are defined as geographically-cohesive phenotypes across defined ranges and are allopatric from related subspecies. *Anthocharis midea* defies our current understanding of this concept, rather consisting of a variable, polytypic form-complex based on the orange male apical patches and degree of dorsal black scaling on the base of the adult wings. While dos Passos & Klots (1969) made headway in our understanding of *midea* and its subspecies, the authors had somewhat limited access to specimens. Gatrell (1998) provided additional information. With the availability of online imagery, we are now able to revisit their findings and develop a much better understanding of this complex.

INTRODUCTION

The appropriately named “Falcate Orangetip” was originally illustrated and labeled as *Mancipium vorax Midea* (Hübner [1809]) but without verbal description (**Fig. 1**) or locational information. The apical orange patch in the male extends inward from the apex and encloses the discal black spot of the forewing. Though not depicted in the original illustration, a small percentage of males display a faint cloud of orange on the outer (apical) portion of the hindwing.

Fig. 1. Original illustrations from Hübner (1809). Male, left image; female, right image.

Dos Passos & Klots (1969) produced an extensive review of regional variation in *A. midea* and designated a neotype of *A. m. midea* from “Wilmington I., near Savannah, Georgia” matching the phenotype illustrated by Hübner (1809). The authors stated: “The chief, if not the only reliable, character in which *A. midea* shows significant geographic variation is the extent of the apical orange patch on the upper side of the forewings of the male...Unfortunately, little or no material from several important regions was available for study.” In that work, they described a new subspecies from West Rock, New Haven, Connecticut, which they named *A. midea annickae*. This type locality is at the farthest northeastern extremity of the species’ range. Subspecies *annickae* is differentiated from nominotypical *A. m. midea* in that the apical orange patch is more restricted in size (**Fig. 2(B)**). Females of both subspecies are indistinguishable from each other (**Figs. 2(G) and 2(H)**).

Dos Passos & Klots produced a table in which 320 male specimens were divided into 7 “pattern groups”, A through G, based on the extent of the male apical orange patch. For the purposes of the present study, groups A and B, in which the orange patch touches or encloses the black discal spot, are referred to here as the “**large-patch**” group, analogous to nominotypical *midea* (**Figs. 1, 2(D)**). Groups F and G are here referred to as the “**small-patch**” group in the present study, analogous to subspecies *annickae* (**Fig. 2(B)**), which are identified by the greatly reduced size of the male apical orange patch. However, in the

present study, the “small” patch is defined as extending approximately 50-65% the distance from the forewing hook to the black discal spot. “**Intermediate-patch**” specimens, in which the patch is greatly enlarged, but not touching the black discal spot, are recorded separately in the present study. These would include those specimens placed in groups C, D and E by dos Passos & Klots (**Fig. 2(C)**). However, in the present study, the intermediate patch is defined as being greater than a distance of approximately 65% from the forewing hook, to the discal spot, but not touching the discal spot (generally leaving a white space between the patch and discal spot, equaling the size of the discal spot).

Of note, “large-patch” specimens in the present study, that were previously assigned to groups A and B of dos Passos & Klots, comprised 89.9% of all their examined specimens (n=33) of *A. midea* in coastal Georgia and South Carolina, leaving 10.1% in the “intermediate-patch” group and 0% in the “small-patch” group. This is corroborated by the observations of Gatrell (1998) of the predominance of large-patch individuals in the Georgia and South Carolina coastal region. By comparison, a small number of specimens analyzed in the present study from those same coastal areas were also of the “small patch” variants. I suspect there may have been some sampling bias in the series that dos Passos & Klots and Gatrell examined. Dos Passos & Klots also noted in their analysis, that nearly half of specimens from both Hinds Co., Mississippi and Baron Co., Missouri, could be assigned to either *midea* or *annickae*, but they lacked material from much of the inland region west of the Appalachians, here recognized as *midea*.

Fig. 2. (A) Intermediate-patch male with light wing base (subspecies *texana*. Wise Co., Texas). (B) Small-patch male (subspecies *annickae*. New Haven Co., Connecticut). (C) Intermediate-patch male (subspecies *midea*. St. Francois Co., Missouri). (D) Large-patch male (subspecies *midea*. St. Francois Co., Missouri). (E) Large-patch male with orange tint on hindwings (subspecies *midea*. Colleton Co., South Carolina). (F) Female with light wing base (subspecies *texana*. Smith Co., Texas). (G) Female (subspecies *annickae*. Frederick Co., Virginia). (H) Female (subspecies *midea*. Colleton Co., South Carolina). (I) Female with orange-tinted apical patch (subspecies *annickae*. Montgomery Co., Maryland).

Dos Passos & Klots (1969) summarized this well: “The matter of referring populations to one subspecies or another is subjective and can only be done on the basis of material available at the moment. Such decisions are always subject to review as new populations and more specimens come under study.”

Gatrelle (1998), having sampled additional *midea* populations in South Carolina and Georgia, believed the large-patched *A. m. midea* is restricted to the coastal islands and immediate coast of Georgia and South Carolina, with *A. m. annickae* occupying the inland Sandhills region within 40 km of coastal *A. m. midea*. Gatrelle’s samples indicated that 20-50% of coastal *midea* males possess an orange tint on the apical portion of the hindwings, representing extreme development of the orange markings. I have only observed two out of 20 males from Edisto Beach, S.C., making my percentage somewhat smaller (10%). While Gatrelle felt that the large-patched *midea* male variants were “rare” inland, he indicated that, over a 30-year period, he observed subspecies *midea* “further and further inland and *annickae* closer and closer to the coast.” I suspect that Gatrelle’s further sampling simply revealed the greater degree of variation already present in South Carolina and Georgia. Dos Passos & Klots had indicated “The population of inland Georgia above the fall line is also characterized by an extensive orange patch, but this is less extensive and less consistent...than in the coastal one.” They concluded that there is a north-south cline east of the Appalachians from Connecticut to Georgia, with “a major break” south of Virginia. The late William Grooms and I have personally sampled (collect and net-release) over 143 specimens since 1988 from northern Virginia and central Maryland, and conclude that nearly 100% of *midea* are of the small-patched form, with the sole exception of a single large-patched individual from Fairfax County, no doubt an aberrant in this region. More recent sampling via collections and online imagery indicates a more complex picture throughout the species range.

METHODOLOGY

A series of maps was produced by analyzing a variety of sources including imagery from iNaturalist (iNat) and Butterfliesandmoths.org (BAMONA), as well as specimens in the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History (NMNH), American Museum of Natural History (AMNH), the collections of Steve Spomer, Ricky Patterson, the late Ron Gatrelle, and my personal collection, and lastly a variety of online image galleries and literature sources. Specimens are here divided into three groups based on the extent of the male orange apical patch, which, in turn are based on groups A through G established by dos Passos & Klots (1969): small-patch (groups F, G) (**Figs. 2(B)**); intermediate-patch (groups C, D, E) (**Fig. 2(A, C)**); and large-patch (groups A, B) (**Figs. 2(D, E)**). Subspecies *texana* (Gatrelle, 1998) (**Fig. 2(A)**) was mapped separately, based on a single character (clear white dorsal wing bases). In the case of *texana*, females were included in the analysis along with males. Females of nominotypical *midea* and subspecies *annickae* are virtually indistinguishable, thus not mapped.

First, individuals of the small-patched variant, based on dos Passos & Klots (1969) groups F and G were mapped (**Fig. 3**). This variant form approximates what has been traditionally considered subspecies *annickae*. It is immediately apparent that this variant form occurs range-wide, but dominates the eastern portion of the species’ range from Massachusetts to South Carolina and just west into the Ohio River drainage. Small-patched individuals again dominate the western edge of the species’ range from Texas to Kansas, and east into the Mississippi River drainage, as subspecies *texana*. Next, individuals of the intermediate-patched variant were mapped (**Fig. 4**), based on dos Passos & Klots (1969) groups C, D and E. Interestingly, these variants dominated the central portion of the species’ range, from North Carolina across to the eastern edge of Texas, Oklahoma and Kansas.

Individuals of the large-patched variant were then mapped (**Fig. 5**), based on dos Passos & Klots (1969) groups A and B. This variant form approximates what has been traditionally considered nominotypical subspecies *midea*. However, it is important to note that large-patched *midea* range broadly

from the South Carolina/Georgia coast across to the eastern edge of Texas, Oklahoma and Kansas and north into the Missouri and Ohio River drainages, with outlier records in northern Virginia, Washington D.C. and northern New Jersey [outliers are more likely to be documented around major urban centers, due to a greater number of collectors and photographers].

Most individuals in the eastern portion of the species' range display dorsal dark scales at the base of the wings (**Figs. 2(B, C, D, E, G, H, I)**), whereas most individuals in the far western edge of the species' range do not display this dark scaling (**Figs. 2(A, F)**), having the dorsal wing bases entirely white. Those are considered subspecies *texana*. Both of these variant basal forms are mapped here (**Fig. 6**), showing distribution of individuals with clear white wing bases (*texana*), individuals with black wing bases ("not-*texana*") and areas where both types are present, indicating a blend zone or zone of secondary contact (Gatrelle, 1998). This latter finding was rather surprising, as infrequent individuals meeting the description of *texana* were recorded well eastward, as far as South Carolina.

Finally, all four maps are combined to obtain an overall picture showing distribution of maximum orange apical patch size, with distribution of *texana* overlaid (**Fig. 7**). This map was then simplified (**Fig. 8**) to show the approximate range of each subspecies: *annickae*, *texana*, and *midea*, with *midea* divided into a *texana*-influenced intermediate western zone in which both white and black wing-base adults occur, whereas "typical" black wing-base adults dominate in the eastern portion. Continued sampling, either photography or collection-based, will be needed to fill in gaps in the range.

Lastly, additional maps were created to determine regional distribution of females displaying orange tinted forewing apical areas, corresponding to the male orange patch (**Fig. 9**). Distribution of large-patched males displaying orange tint on the outer portion of the hindwings was also mapped (**Fig. 10**). This orange tint on the male hindwings highlights maximum development of the nominotypical "*midea*" form.

Fig. 3. County distribution of "small-patched" variants (shown in yellow).

Fig. 4. County distribution of "intermediate-patched" variants (shown in orange).

Fig. 5. County distribution of “large-patched” variants (shown in red).

Fig. 6. County distribution of variants with white wing bases (subspecies *texana*) shown as blue; black wing bases (that are considered “not-*texana*”) shown as yellow. Green counties indicate BOTH types present.

Fig. 7. Composite map showing distribution of maximum orange patch size throughout range of *A. midea*: RED = large patch; ORANGE = intermediate patch; YELLOW = small patch; GREY= additional sight and literature records, including all females; BLACK DOT = white dorsal wing base (*texana*).

Fig. 8. Generalized ranges of subspecies. Stars indicate type localities: yellow = *annickae*; red = *midea*; blue = *texana*.

Fig. 9. County distribution of females displaying orange-tinted forewing apex (shown in orange).

Fig. 10. County distribution of males displaying orange-tinted hindwings (shown in red).

Finally, a sample of male apical orange patch size (**Table 1**) shows percentages of each of the three apical patch variants in different regions of the United States. Percentages and counts are based per county, while some adjacent counties are grouped to produce more reliable results.

State	Location	small patch	intermediate patch	large patch
AR	Polk, Scott Co's.	0% (n=0)	57% (n=8)	43% (n=6)
CT	New Haven Co.	52% (n=12)	48% (n=11)	0% (n=0)
GA	Chatham, Glynn Co's.	0% (n=0)	9% (n=2)	91% (n=21)
GA	Cobb, DeKalb, Fulton Co's.	0% (n=0)	54% (n=13)	46% (n=11)
KS	Johnson Co.	0% (n=0)	44% (n=4)	56% (n=5)
MD	Allegany Co.	100% (n=9)	0% (n=0)	0% (n=0)
MD	Frederick & Montgomery Co's.	100% (n=68)	0% (n=0)	0% (n=0)
MO	Barry Co.	0% (n=0)	20% (n=2)	80% (n=8)
MO	Benton Co.	0% (n=0)	48% (n=22)	52% (n=24)
MO	Christian Co.	0% (n=0)	56% (n=5)	44% (n=4)
MO	St. Francois Co.	10% (n=2)	30% (n=6)	60% (n=12)
MO	St. Louis Co.	0% (n=0)	67% (n=6)	33% (n=3)
MS	Calhoun, Lafayette, Panola, Pontotoc Co's.	0% (n=0)	43% (n=3)	57% (n=4)
MS	Claiborne, Hinds, Madison, Warren Co's.	0% (n=0)	47% (n=40)	53% (n=45)
NJ	Essex & Passaic Co's.	69% (n=18)	27% (n=7)	4% (n=1)
NY	Orange & Rockland Co's.	37% (n=7)	63% (n=12)	0% (n=0)
OK	Garvin Co.	0% (n=0)	100% (n=6)	0% (n=0)
SC	Beaufort, Charleston, Colleton Co's.	6% (n=2)	12% (n=4)	83% (n=27)
VA	Frederick Co.	100% (n=45)	0% (n=0)	0% (n=0)
VA	Fairfax, Loudoun Cos.	98% (n=73)	1% (n=1)	1% (n=1)

Table 1. Sample distribution of male apical patch size showing percentage of each of the three variant forms. Adjacent counties are grouped for more reliable percentages.

CONCLUSION

Anthocharis midea is more accurately described as consisting of a form complex that is difficult to characterize as a traditional grouping of subspecies. Keeping with prevailing concepts, the distribution of the three described and currently-recognized subspecies needed to be better defined, based on the phenotypic characteristics in the four groups shown in the final map (**Fig. 8**). Males primarily fall into two variants, based on the dorsal orange apical patch, and presence or absence of black scales at the base of the wings. Females are indistinguishable to subspecies except by the presence or absence of black scales at the base of the wings.

***Anthocharis midea midea* (Hübner, [1809])** – This is a highly polytypic grouping, consisting of varying sizes of male orange apical-patched individuals. Percentages of localized populations displaying small, intermediate or large apical patches fluctuates widely across the entire region shown here as *midea*. A most interesting finding was that large and intermediate-patched individuals dominate the central region of the species, with small-patched variants being much less frequent than in eastern (*annickae*) or western (*texana*) portions of the species range. The range of ssp. *midea* shown here is considerably larger than has been traditionally considered - just along the southeastern coastal region where large-patched individuals are more frequent (Gatrelle, 1998), but is best defined as the region where the large and intermediate-patched variant forms occur. Males with orange-tinted hindwings show maximum development of dorsal orange coloration.

***Anthocharis midea annickae* dos Passos & Klots, 1969** – The small-patched male variant occurs range-wide, from Massachusetts to Mexico. Subspecies *annickae* is thus best defined as the portion of the species range displaying the small apical patch to the general exclusion of large and intermediate patched males, and with black dorsal wing bases. The range extends from Massachusetts to Georgia and west into the Ohio River drainage.

***Anthocharis midea texana* Gatrelle, 1998** – This subspecies is based entirely on a single character – the presence of white dorsal wing bases. In much of the subspecies' range, males appear similar to subspecies *annickae*, but lack the black wing bases of *annickae*. Toward the eastern portion of the range of *texana*, many male individuals are found, with intermediate and large apical patches. This subspecies then grades eastward into the following grouping:

Anthocharis midea midea/texana intermediates – This region displays the broadest range of polytypic individuals. Male apical patches may be small, large, or intermediate. Adults of both sexes may display either black (*midea*) or white (*texana*) wing bases.

Lastly, females displaying the orange-tinted forewing apical area do not precisely correspond to the above variants. Gatrelle (1998) believed that females possessing the orange-tinted apex are confined to the southeastern coastal region. With further sampling and updated imagery, these have been observed range wide in subspecies *midea* and *annickae*, but have not yet been documented in subspecies *texana*. Orange-tinted females are apparently more frequent within the range of polytypic ssp. *midea* (**Fig. 9**). The documented presence of orange-tinted females centered in the region around the state of Maryland is very likely the result of a greater number of collectors and photographers concentrated in that region. This indicates that orange-tinted females are likely present anywhere within the range of ssp. *annickae*.

It can be concluded that *A. midea* is a highly polytypic form-complex. Nominotypical *A. m. midea* is a polytypic, variable “subspecies”, occupying the central portion of the species range. The large-patched males appear more frequently along the Georgia and South Carolina coastal region but also frequently within a patchwork of colonies as far inland as Oklahoma and Nebraska. Subspecies *annickae* is best restricted to the northeastern region where only the small-patched variants occur, to the exclusion of

intermediate or large-patched males (except for rare aberrant individuals). Subspecies *texana* is restricted to the southwestern portion of the species range, where individuals lack the dorsal dark basal scales and males bear small apical patches to the exclusion of intermediate or large-patched males (though aberrants have been documented). There is a very broad area from Kansas to Mississippi where *texana* and *midea* variants intergrade, but might be considered within polytypic subspecies *midea*. In this intergrade region, individuals with light wing bases are more frequent toward the west, and dark wing-base individuals are more frequent toward the east. I propose no changes in subspecies designations, rather suggesting that the concept of subspecies stands to be redefined in the case of *A. midea*, to reflect the distribution of the discussed variant forms.

NOMENCLATURE

Of interest in the study of *Anthocharis midea* are the numerous nomenclatural changes published throughout literature. Many of the following were applied in different combinations or treatments; too many to list here. Following is a simplified synonymy:

[genus] ***Anthocharis*** Boisduval, Rambur, [Duménil] & Graslin (1833)

=*Mancipium* Hübner, [1809] (preoccupied name)

=*Falcapica* Klots, 1930 (proposed replacement name)

=*Anthochris* Cook, 1948 (misspelling)

=*Anthocaris* auct. (misspelling)

As *Papilio* Fabricius, 1793

As *Synchloe* Hübner, [1818]

As *Pieris* (Godart, 1819)

As *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819]

As *Tetracharis* Grote, 1898

[subgenus] ***Tetracharis*** Grote, 1898

=*Midea* Herrich-Schäffer, 1867 (preoccupied name)

As *Paramidea* Kuznetsov, 1929

A. midea midea (Hübner, [1809])

=*genutia* (Fabricius, 1793) (preoccupied name)

=*lherminieri* (Godart, [1819])

=*flavida* (Skinner, 1917)

=*medea* (Leussler, 1938) (misspelling)

A. midea annickae (dos Passos & Klots, 1969)

A. midea texana Gatrell, 1998

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LITERATURE

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Hübner, J. 1806. *Sammlung Exotischer Schmetterlinge*. First Band. Published by author: 436 pp. [pl. 142, figs. 1-4].

ADDITIONAL SOURCES OF IMAGERY

Butterflies and Moths of North America <https://www.butterfliesandmoths.org>

Butterflies of America <https://butterfliesofamerica.com>

eButterfly <https://www.e-butterfly.org>

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